

Sovereign AI: Digital Decolonization through Sarvam-105B in Libraries

Madhumita Neogi¹
Parthasarathi Mukhopadhyay²

Abstract

This study evaluates the effectiveness of Sarvam-105B - India's flagship sovereign large language model - in complex library operations. The research utilizes a framework based on our prior work, employing OpenRefine as a front-end data transformation tool and its AI extension, which was configured using the API key, model name, and chat completion URL of Sarvam AI. The contextual precision of Sarvam-105B was demonstrated across five core library operations: genderization of author names, translation of technical abstracts, summarization of scholarly content, sentiment analysis, and multilingual bibliographic record generation. Due to its extensive training on Indic corpora, Sarvam-105B exhibited high linguistic precision, particularly in major Indian languages. Methodologically, the 'connected' approach - such as name transliteration prior to genderization or summarization derived from translated Bengali abstracts - demonstrates that domestic AI is capable of performing complex, multi-layered tasks. The research findings reveal that sovereign LLMs are sufficiently powerful to meet the needs of professional libraries while maintaining linguistic sovereignty, cultural integrity, and data security. The study provides a road map for implementing a sovereign AI stack in libraries that prioritize regional accuracy over foreign proprietary models.

Keywords: Digital Decolonization, Multilingual Data Processing, OpenRefine, Sovereign AI, Sarvam-105B

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1. From Dependence to Decolonization: Defining the Sovereign Ai Initiative

The significant transformation of Large Language Models (LLMs) is revolutionizing domain-specific information retrieval, automated reasoning, and educational evaluation. As AI is becoming one of the most crucial aspects for the country's infrastructure, the concept of sovereign AI has become an essential strategy that is required for reducing dependency on foreign, proprietary, English-centric models from the USA, Europe, or China (Jang, 2025). The concept refers to a nation's ability to develop, host, and govern AI systems that harmonize with its own cultural, linguistic, and regulatory frameworks. For a data-driven and linguistically diverse country like India, the potential benefits of sovereign AI have become very significant, and this transition is not only about technological equality but also ensures that the AI system understands and serves the local context of more than a billion citizens.

Data sovereignty, infrastructure sovereignty, model sovereignty, and workforce sovereignty are the four pillars of 'Sovereign AI.' These pillars enable strategic autonomy and ensure that the

¹Madhumita Neogi, Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, 741235 email id: madhumitalis25@klyuniv.ac.in,*Corresponding author,
²Parthasarathi Mukhopadhyay, Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, 741235 email id: psm@klyuniv.ac.in

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Madhumita Neogi*

Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, 741235

email id: madhumitalis25@klyuniv.ac.in

Parthasarathi Mukhopadhyay

Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, 741235

email id: psm@klyuniv.ac.in

***Corresponding author**

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the effectiveness of Sarvam-105B India's flagship sovereign large language model, in complex library operations. The framework is based on our prior research. The framework includes OpenRefine as a front-end data transformation tool and its AI extension which is configured by using API key, model name and chat completion URL of Sarvam AI. The contextual precision of Sarvam-105B demonstrated across five core library operations: genderization of author names, translation of technical abstract, summarization of abstract, sentiment analysis, multilingual bibliographic record generation.

Because of the extensive training in Indic corpora Sarvam-105B has higher linguistic precision, especially in the major Indian languages. In methodology, the 'connected' approach like transliteration of names before genderization or summarization from translated Bengali abstract shows that domestic AI is capable of performing complex, multi-layer tasks. The research findings reveal that sovereign LLMs are powerful enough to fulfill the needs of professional libraries and also maintain linguistic sovereignty, cultural integrity and data sovereignty. The study provides a roadmap for implementing sovereign AI stack into the libraries that prioritize regional accuracy compared to foreign proprietary LLMs.

Keywords: *Sovereign AI, Sarvam-105B, OpenRefine, Library Services.*

1. FROM DEPENDENCE TO DECOLONIZATION: DEFINING THE SOVEREIGN AI INITIATIVE

The significant transformation of Large Language Models (LLMs) is revolutionizing domain-specific information retrieval, automated reasoning, and educational evaluation. As AI is becoming one of the most crucial aspects for the country's infrastructure, the concept of sovereign AI has become an essential strategy that is required for reducing the dependency on foreign proprietary, English-centric models of USA, European countries or China (Jang, 2025). The concept refers to a nation's ability to develop, host, and govern AI systems that harmonize with its own cultural, linguistic, and regulatory frameworks. For a data-driven and linguistically diverse country like India, the potential benefits of sovereign AI have become very high, and this transition is not only about technological equality but also ensures that the AI system understands and serves the local context of more than a billion citizens.

Data sovereignty, infrastructure sovereignty, model sovereignty, and workforce sovereignty are the four pillars of 'Sovereign AI.' These pillars enable strategic autonomy and ensure that the nation is not only a consumer of foreign technology but also an innovator of its own. In the context of information science, these pillars empower libraries to move beyond 'black-box' proprietary

systems. By utilizing domestic models trained on local linguistic characteristics, libraries can ensure that the security standards and cultural sensitivities of the nation are embedded directly into the discovery layer of their collections.

Sovereign AI has now become a global trend because nowadays every developing nation considers AI as a critical component of national security and economic development (Dale, 2025). By developing domestic AI systems, a nation aims to protect sensitive data from foreign countries and also ensures that AI models reflect their own cultural values and languages in comparison to globally known AI models. Ultimately, this initiative is beyond basic data sovereignty to assure technical autonomy in which a country is not completely dependent on foreign proprietary models and also to minimize 'knowledge colonization' and ensure data security by assuring that AI systems are in sync with regional legislation, cultural peculiarities, and strategic national interests.

2. GLOBAL INITIATIVES IN SOVEREIGN AI

The need for sovereign AI appears as an important aspect in the global technical revolution. Due to the limitations of generic, foreign-hosted large language models (LLMs), particularly in regard to data origin, linguistic bias, and high cost—nations are now investing in an 'AI stack' that is fully under their national control. A comprehensive breakdown of specific global sovereign AI initiatives across various regions is provided in *Annexure I*.

2.1 North America:

The approach of national AI strategy was first launched by Canada in 2017. This approach of sovereignty emphasizes building a research-driven ecosystem for AI that has dedicated analysis capabilities. They start Pan-Canadian AI by investing 125 million dollars. It focuses on deep-learning research through various institutes. But the sovereign AI compute strategy was launched in 2024 to fulfill the need of physical infrastructure. They offered a \$24 billion package to Canadian researchers and startups to build a sovereign AI for the country.

2.2 Southeastern Asia:-

The sovereign AI initiatives of China started with "AI Plus" initiatives and the 15th five-year plan (2026-2030), whose objective is to transform AI from a commercial tool to a national strategic utility. Baidu, Alibaba, Tencent, Huawei, iFlyTek, and DeepSeek are the companies that lead the sovereign AI initiatives in China. ERNIE, Qwen, Hunyuan, Pangu, Spark, and DeepSeek are the developed LLMs by these companies. Qwen is known for its excellent performance in coding and mathematics, while Pangu was developed as an industry-specific model. ERNIE 4.5 and Hunyuan-Pro have more than one trillion parameters. 'AI Bridging Cloud Infrastructure (ABCI)' is an initiative by Japan that provides GPU infrastructure to their domestic companies and researchers to develop sovereign LLMs. The government of Japan also provides subsidies to local startups who aim to build 'Made-in-Japan' AI, which is trained on Japanese scientific and cultural data to ensure technological sovereignty. South Korea already has a strong domestic tech ecosystem to build a 'full-stack sovereign AI' system. South Korea also passed a law, which states government support is mandatory for AI data centers and production of domestic training data to ensure technological sovereignty. In 2019, the 'National AI Strategy' was launched by the Singaporean government. Singapore also established an AI safety institute in 2024 to prepare standards for sovereign AI.

2.3 Middle Eastern Countries:-

The UAE has established itself as a global forefront in sovereign AI initiatives. The UAE is the first country in the world that appointed a minister of state for artificial intelligence in 2017. The UAE successfully launched two open-source models: Falcon, developed by the Technology Innovation Institute (TII) and Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, and Cerebras and Jais, which is an Arabic-first LLM in the world, developed by G42's Inception.

2.4 Europe:-

In Europe, France was the first country that launched a national strategy for the development of an alternative AI system compared to USA and Chinese dominance. According to the report of Cedric Villani, France invested £1.5 billion for research in AI. The Jean Zay supercomputer is the base of French AI sovereignty, as BLOOM (BigScience Large Language Open-access Multilingual Language Model) and Mistral are trained on this supercomputer. Additionally, France recently announced building an exascale supercomputer to support sovereign AI development. The UK has built their own AI Research Resource (AIRR) to provide cloud services for researchers and startups. Isambard-AI and Dawn are the two supercomputers for training massive AI models. In 2025, the UK introduced the 'AI Growth Zone' to decentralize AI power and boost local economies and also launched the 'National Digital Library' from where UK researchers train their models on UK-originated data that is unavailable for foreign commercial LLMs (Girolami & Wooldrige, 2023). Poland also took sovereign AI initiatives and developed an LLM, which is trained on Polish data and generates text in the Polish language (Kocoń et al., 2025; Sułkowski & Ulatowska, 2025). Poland is also an active member of the 'European AI Factory' and made the Gaia AI factory, which is managed by Cyfronet AGH in Krakow. It provides massive GPU support to the researchers. The aim of Polish sovereign AI initiatives is to implement the model both in the civilian economy and national defense. KI-Norge is a coordination to promote the sovereign AI trend in Norway. Its goal is to train an LLM in the Norwegian language and legal standards. Norway is the first country that launched maritime-specific sovereign AI in 2025 that ensures the shipping industry of Norway uses domestic technologies.

Additionally, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, and the Netherlands invested millions of dollars to encourage researchers to build a domestic AI system that is also trained in local data.

3. INDIAN INITIATIVES IN SOVEREIGN AI

India's journey in sovereign AI began in 2018 when NITI Ayog introduced the 'National Strategy for AI.' Later, the government of India sanctioned 10,372 crore rupees for the Indian AI mission in 2024 (Singh, 2025). A comprehensive list of these domestic initiatives and their technical specifications is provided in Table 1. BharatGen is the result of this mission; it is a multimodal large language model family. It generates high-quality text, audio, and images in the response of 22 Indian languages. Param-1 is the key model of this family and has 3 to 7 billion parameters. Additionally, Patram7B Instruct is the first Vision-Language Model (VLM) of India that can interpret Indian governmental documents, forms, and scripts in regional languages with high accuracy. There are some sector-specific sovereign AI projects like Health AI (trained on indigenous clinical data), Krishi-AI for crop yield prediction and pest management, and Gov-AI for administrative tasks, policy drafting, etc.

Meanwhile, Bhashini (Bhasha Interface for India) is the foundational pillar of India's linguistic sovereignty. It covers 22 official languages of India and translates in 1 second/sentence with 95% accuracy. It has specialized applications to solve specific linguistic hurdles:

- *Anuvaad*: Text-to-text translation in 22 official languages of India;
- *Chitraanuvaad*: Real-time dubbing and also provide subtitles of the video in Indian languages
- *Lekhaanuvaad*: Digitizes and translates handwritten scripts and official governmental documents;
- *Shrutilekh*: Real-time speech transcription system;
- *Vaanianuvaad*: Real-time speech-to-speech translation that used for meetings and live interaction;
- *Abhilekh*: Voice-to-text application that provides instant real-time transcription, a specialized version of 'Abhilekh' used for transcribing and archiving parliamentary debates in different Indian languages;

- *Converse*: A real-time voice-to-voice translation tool to allow people speaking in different languages to converse instantly. It is used by police personnel for multilingual public assistance and homestay owners in tribal areas to communicate with the tourists.
- Lastly, Bhashini recently launched a speech-to-text application for tribal languages called *Aadi Vaani*, to ensure that low-resource languages are also part of sovereign digital stack.

These models are trained on domestic data DPI like *AIKosh*, which hosts 6,250 curated datasets and 243 AI models, and Bharat Data Sagar, which is the largest repository for India-centric data, including more than 15,000 hours of annotated voice data in 22 official languages of India. On the other hand to solve the lack of digital data in regional languages, *Bhashini* uses a crowd-sourcing platform called *BhashaDaan*. It also have four parts like Suniyebhasha, Likhiebhasha, Dekhiyebhasha, and Boliyebhasha. Bhashini’s most significant deployment is in Maha Kumbh 2025 where it provides Kumbh Sah‘AI’yak chatbot to assist millions of pilgrims in 11 different languages. And also integrated into the ‘My Aadhaar’ portal to navigate citizens in their mother tongue.

The key domestic Large Language Models (LLMs) currently driving India’s sovereign AI landscape, including their developers and core characteristics, are summarized in Table 1.

Table-1: Indian Sovereign AI initiatives

Sl. No.	Name of the LLM and Latest Version	Developed by	Launched in	Parameters	Initiative type	Details
1	Sarvam (Sarvam-M)	2023	Sarvam AI	24 billion	Govt. aided startup	It is the first startup selected under the IndiaAI Mission. Sarvam-M is built on the Mistral Small architecture and supports more than 10 Indian languages.
	Sarvam-30B & 105B	2026	Sarvam AI	30 & 105 billion	Govt. aided startup	This MoE model perform well in reasoning, programming and agentic tasks.
2	Krutrim (Krutrim-2)	2024	OLA Krutrim Labs	12 billion	Private	It is built on Mistral-NeMo 12B architecture. Krutrim-2 supports more than 20 Indian languages.
3	BharatGPT (BharatGPT mini)	2024, 2025	CoRover.ai	534 billion	Private (strategic partner for govt. portals like GSTN and IRCTC)	It supports 14 Indic languages and integrated with real-time Indian datasets like Aadhar, GST. It is Edge-AI capable and also works in offline.
4	Hanooman	2024	Seetha Mahalaxmi Healthcare and IIT Bombay	1.5 to 40 billion (MoE)	Private-Academic collaboration and also supported by Reliance	It is a multimodel LLM that supports more than 98 global languages including 12 major Indian languages, and fine-tuned for healthcare and governance.
5	Gan-V	2025	Gan.ai	7 billion	Govt. aided startup	It is leading project in India’s sovereign AI Mission for generating video and voice. It creates hyper-realistic videos where voice and lip-syncing are perfectly matched to a specific user or context.
6	Soket-L	2025	Soket AI Labs	7 to 13 billion	Govt. aided startup	It focuses on defense and healthcare sectors and supports 22 official Indian languages.
7	Gnani-Voice LLM (Dhwani)	2025	Gnani.ai	14 billion	Govt. aided startup	It is a voice to voice LLM and supports more than 12 Indic languages. It can handle over 30 million voice interaction daily and used in banking and insurance sectors. It also work as ‘Agentic AI’

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Recent studies demonstrate that LLMs are geographically biased and have a tendency to favor locations that have higher socioeconomic conditions and also aligned to western-centric contexts (Dennison et al., 2025; Manvi et al., 2024). Researchers also used dataset to evaluate the performance of global LLMs in multilingual contexts and domain-specific knowledge (Gopinadh et al., 2026; Romanou et al., 2024).

The concept of sovereign AI gained significant attention in recent years. Researchers have explore the implications of AI on global governance and how the concept of digital sovereignty can reshape the AI landscape (Mellaoui et al., 2025; Roberts, 2025; Roberts & Ziosi, 2025). According to Averyanov et al. (2023), strategic development in AI taking place in Russia, and national strategies are needed to maintain scientific and technological sovereignty. They also compare Russia's national strategies for AI with USA and China, and recognize the growth and effective implementation in Russia. Around 240 research studies on digital sovereignty evaluated by (Repetto, 2025) and categorize according to their discipline. The concept of sovereignty needs to be analyzed and highlight the lack of implementation in different contexts. AI systems are now crucial for international affairs, and the global governance of AI forces to achieve digital sovereignty (Srivastava & Bullock, 2024). Some researchers have proposed a framework for sovereign AI (Singh & Sengupta, 2025; Wang, 2025). There is a global competition for sovereign AI, and digital geopolitics have been affected by this (Wang, 2025). Researchers state that digital sovereignty and data sovereignty are the base of sovereign AI (Altendeitering et al., 2022; Roberts, 2024). Global collaboration and open-source projects influenced the nations to take initiatives in sovereign AI (Gerosa et al., 2025). Sovereignty should be interpreted as an authority concept of those bastions of governance, rather than control (Lee, 2025; Roberts, 2024).

To reduce control over digital infrastructure and data, many countries and organizations aim to develop their own AI system (Abbas et al., 2025; Bouhlaoui, 2025). Fanar and HUMAINChat are notable examples of this. Fanar is an Arabic-centric multimodal generative AI platform that supports language, speech, and image generation tasks. This AI platform is powered by two Arabic LLMs, i.e., Fanar Star and Fanar Prime; these models are trained on a 1 trillion dataset. The design, development, and implementation were sponsored by Qatar's Ministry of Communication and Technology at Hamad Bin Khalifa University's Qatar Computing Research Institute (Abbas et al., 2025). On the other hand, HUMAINChat is a sovereign AI chatbot that is developed in Saudi Arabia. The chatbot 'HUMAINChat' is designed to provide a deep dive into the capabilities of sovereign AI in the region as well as this type of application, highlighting the concept of digital sovereignty and data sovereignty. Although the study also highlighted the limitations of such chatbots, like the need for large amounts of data. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance and need for sovereignty in this digital era to control their own data and AI systems (Bouhlaoui, 2025).

In recent few years implementation of AI and ML in libraries has been a growing trend, researchers demonstrate the potential ability of AI and ML in library services like subject indexing, information retrieval and natural language processing and prove the effectiveness and accuracy in library operations (Ahmed et al., 2023; Dasgupta et al., 2025; Mitra & Mukhopadhyay, 2023; Neogi et al., 2025). A semi-automated subject indexing system is developed by using Annif framework and LCSH and Homosaurus as the vocabulary system (Ahmed et al., 2023; Mitra & Mukhopadhyay, 2023). Some of the researcher (Neogi et al., 2025; Dasgupta et al., 2025) also designed a framework by utilizing Model Context Protocol (MCP) to connect Claude Sonnet (as a front-end LLM) and VuFind (as a back-end open source library service platform) and DSpace (as a back-end digital repository software). Although they have identified some limitations related to structured queries and security concerns. Deployment of LLMs in library services can improve the efficiency and user

experience. LLMs also can help to automate repetitive operations in library, improve the information retrieval and document delivery services (Neogi & Mukhopadhyay, 2025).

While previous studies have successfully deployed global LLMs like Claude Sonnet 4, Gemini 2.5 Pro in library operations but the paradigm now shift toward the proficiency of sovereign models and there is a critical need to assess these workflows by using a sovereign, Indic-centric model to handle regional linguistic distinctions and ensure data sovereignty in the context of Indian libraries.

5. OBJECTIVES

This research explores the paradigm shift from global LLMs to sovereign LLMs which is more crucial for ensuring national data autonomy and cultural integrity within knowledge institutions. Moving from global models, libraries can utilize domestic AI stacks like Sarvam-105B to achieve higher linguistic accuracy and data security.

- To explain the necessity of domestic AI regarding to national data security and linguistic representation specifically in regional languages
- To illustrate international and national initiatives of sovereign AI
- To demonstrate the effectiveness of Sarvam-105B in core library operations particularly in multilingual contexts.

This research study proposes a realistic framework for deploying sovereign model (Sarvam-105B) to moving forward more secure, culturally resonant and dynamic library system.

6. TRANSITION FROM GLOBAL LLM to SOVEREIGN LLM IMPLEMENTATION

The methodology used in this study is based on the programmatic approach which is proposed by (Neogi & Mukhopadhyay, 2025). They have developed the framework on a Linux-based environment and used OpenRefine as an open-source data transmission tool. In the previous study we have demonstrate the successful deployment of Gemini 2.5 Pro to perform the complex library operations. Now in this current research study framework remains same but instead of Gemini 2.5 Pro we incorporate Sarvam-105B which is India's flagship sovereign LLM. Moving beyond a simple comparative performance evaluation, this study serves as a functional demonstration. It demonstrates that sovereign LLMs are now powerful enough to handle the complex multi-layered requirements of a library. Moreover the this transformation proves the effectiveness of a sovereign LLM in the regional, script-specific context, particularly in Bengali language ecosystem.

6.1 System Installation and Configuration

In this study we followed the framework of our previous study. The system configured on a Ubuntu 24.04 LTS. OpenRefine, which is an open-source tool that can handle large-scale messy data. Here OpenRefine worked as the core of data transformation layer. The system environment remains unchanged with our previously tested framework to ensure that the core infrastructure is stable and validated through research.

6.2 Installation and Configuration of AI Extension

The AI extension of OpenRefine developed by Sunil Natraj has enriched OpenRefine. It flawlessly integrate LLMs into the process of data transformation. While previous framework utilize Gemini 2.5 Pro as the brain for data processing. The research reconfigures the AI extension with Sarvam-105B API key and the chat completion URL of Sarvam.ai. This transition highlights the flexible nature of the framework and proves that national AI system can be implemented within existing library system without calling for a redesign of the system architecture. The specific configuration interface for integrating Sarvam-105B within OpenRefine is illustrated in Figure 1.

LLM Provider

Label

Server URL

Model

API Key

Temperature

Top-P

Seed

Max tokens

Wait Time (milliseconds)

Figure-1: Configuration of Sarvam-105B within the OpenRefine

6.3 Selection of Case Studies

To ensure consistency in the sovereign model’s performance this research replicated the five case studies defined in our previous work with some modification to test the model’s linguistic accuracy in regional language:

- Genderization of Bengali names.
- Translation of RAG-focused technical abstracts into Bengali language.
- Summarization of scholarly content (TL;DR) into Bengali language.
- Sentiment Analysis of book reviews which are in Bengali language.
- Multilingual Bibliographic Record Generation (MARC 21) in English and Bengali.

The decision to maintain the same case studies is purposeful; it shifts the research focus from “how to build the framework” to “how a sovereign model performs” within library contexts. This research demonstrates that a sovereign LLM can also handle a complex library task particularly those involving Bengali language or any other regional language with same accuracy as global LLMs.

6.4 Validation of the Extension and Experimental Workflow

After the configuration of AI extension the connectivity was verified through the extension’s in build diagnostic test. Later, this extension was utilized via the ‘Extract by AI’ feature in OpenRefine. Processing of datasets begins with the mapping of specific metadata columns, then this column’s data and specialized prompt use to fetch data from Sarvam-105B. To ensure consistent performance and professional-grade outputs, a structured prompt library was developed for each of the five library operations; these detailed prompts are documented in *Annexure II*. The ‘Generate Preview’ feature allows to ensure configuration accuracy and linguistic reliability before committing transformation to the full library corpus.

7. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

7.1 Genderization

Global LLMs are miscategorizing Bengali names due to the limited cultural context to differentiate between masculine and feminine suffixes in specific regional dialects. This problem can be solved by sovereign LLMs because the sovereign models are trained on local onomastics. In this way, Sarvam-105B can reduce the Western bias errors and ensure that historical records of scholars and authors are correctly identified and preserve the integrity of the library's biographical data.

Method: To help libraries organize author lists, we took names written in English and asked the AI to write them in Bengali script. Because many Bengali names have special endings that show if a person is male or female, we then asked the AI to guess the gender. This helps the library know more about the authors in their collection. The successful gender identification of Bengali names is shown in Figure 2.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "Extract using AI from column authorships.author.display_name". It has several configuration options: "Column" set to "Add new" with a dropdown and "Genderisation" in a text box; "LLM Provider" set to "Sarvam-105b"; "Response format" set to "Text"; and a description of the task: "You are a Bengali transliteration and name analysis expert. You will be given a list of author names where forenames and surnames are separated by '|'. Your tasks:". There is also a section for "Provide JSON Schema" which is disabled. Below the configuration is a "Preview" section with tabs for "Preview", "History", and "Starred". The "Preview" tab shows a "value" field with the text "Sayan Pal|Abir Das|Soumita Roy|Nilakshi Chakraborty|T. K. Sarkar|Keka Sarkar|Malay Kumar Adak|Sudipta Kumar Sil" and a "response" field with the Bengali output: "সায়ন পাল - পুরুষ", "অবির দাস - পুরুষ", "সৌমিতা রায় - মহিলা", "নীলকণ্ঠী চক্রবর্তী - মহিলা", "সরকার - অজানা", "কেকা সরকার - মহিলা", "মলয় কুমার অদক - পুরুষ", "সুদীপ্ত কুমার সিল - পুরুষ", "মোট পুরুষ লেখক: ৪", "মোট মহিলা লেখক: ৩". There are "Help" and "Generate Preview" buttons, and "OK" and "Cancel" buttons at the bottom.

Figure-2: Gender Identification for Bengali Names

7.2 Translation

This case study bridges the gap between high-end technical research and regional accessibility. Currently “Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)” is a core topic of AI research, and most of the discourse is English-centric. For Indian academic libraries, there is a critical need for equal access to this knowledge. Traditional machine translation often struggles with terminological erosion and tokenization error (insufficient tokens in the regional languages). But unlike global models, Sarvam-105B was trained on 12 trillion tokens with a high density of Indic data. Due to this, Sarvam-105B can translate technical terms into the Bengali language that match computer science terminology.

Method: We took difficult science reports about AI that were written in English. We asked the Sarvam AI to turn these into Bengali. Unlike normal translation tools, this AI was trained on billions of Indian words, so it understands hard technical words better and makes them sound

natural in Bengali. An example of this contextual translation of a technical abstract is provided in Figure 3.

Figure-3: Contextual Translation in Bengali

7.3 Summarization

In a real-world library discovery system, a user often wants the full abstract and a summary of the abstract in their mother tongue. Global LLMs can summarize English text as well as summarize technical content in Bengali or from an already translated Bengali abstract. But often leads to linguistic bias. By using Sarvam-105B, libraries can fulfill this need for linguistic TL;DRs that maintain scholarly nuances. In this case study Sarvam-105B acts as a ‘Regional Knowledge Synthesizer’ that reduces a full-length Bengali abstract into a lucid summary without losing the core research objectives.

Method: Most people don't have time to read a long five-page summary. We used the AI to read the Bengali version of the science reports and rewrite them into just two or three simple sentences. This lets a student or researcher quickly understand what the paper is about in their own language. The generation of these concise scholarly summaries (TL;DR) in Bengali is displayed in Figure 4.

Figure-4: Generation of Scholarly Summaries (TL;DR) in Bengali

7.4 Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis plays a vital role for collection development in a library. However, global LLMs often fail to understand the complexity of the Indian languages, as these are highly expressive languages where sentiment is conveyed through sarcasm, metaphors, and idioms.

Figure-5: Sentiment Analysis of Indian Language Book Reviews

On the other hand, global LLMs are usually trained on English-centric corpora, and because of this, they often misinterpret them as neutral and fail to capture the actual emotions of the reviewer. As Sarvam-105B is trained on a massive Indic dataset that also includes Bengali literature, it can differentiate between actual disappointment and productive critique. By using sovereign models, which are designed to prioritize user privacy and data security, we can also protect user data from proprietary LLMs that may not have the same level of commitment to safeguarding personal information.

Method: We looked at book reviews written by readers. Sometimes people use sarcasm or local slang to say they didn't like a book. We asked the AI to read these and tell us if the reader was happy or upset. This helps librarians decide which books are popular and which ones they should buy more of. Figure 5 demonstrates the model's performance in sentiment analysis of complex Bengali book reviews. It is interesting to note here that this LLM (Sarovam-105B) has the ability to understand instructions (technically called prompt engineering) in Indian languages. The same sentiment analysis task as depicted in Figure 5 has also been attempted in Bengali language with expected result (Figure 6).

Figure-6: Sentiment Analysis through Prompt in an Indian Language

7.5 Multilingual Bibliographic Record Generation

Linguistic imbalance is a major obstacle of traditional library cataloging. Due to the complexity of inserting regional scripts and the inadequacy of automated tools for dual-script cataloging, the metadata is often limited to English. This obstacle reduces the discoverability of the resources, and on the other hand, creating multilingual records for resources is a labor-intensive process that most Indian libraries cannot afford. Global LLMs often transliterate incorrectly or struggle with the character encoding of Bengali script in a structured MARC format. While Sarvam-105B understands the syntax of both languages, it can generate the corresponding Bengali script for appropriate or repeated tags. Because of the training data sets, Sarvam-105B can differentiate the logic between 'Main Entry' and 'Added Entry' for Indian authors. By using a sovereign model, the

authority control for regional names and titles is easier, as the system understands local bibliographic standards very well.

Method: Libraries use a special "computer code" called a MARC record to keep track of books. Usually, these are only in English. We asked the AI to take the book information and automatically create this code in both English and Bengali. This makes it much easier for people to find books using the library's search computer. This task was bit technical involving the use of Indian scripts in 1XX, 2XX, 6XX etc and corresponding alternative graphics character (Tag 880) for representation ALA-LC based Romanization of Indian scripts. Annexure II includes the complete prompt deployed to achieve this task. The final output of the automated multilingual MARC 21 record generation can be seen in Figure 7.

Extract using AI from column Book Data

Column: Add new (dropdown)
MARC_Record (input field)

LLM Provider: Sarvam-105b (dropdown)

Response format: Text (dropdown)

Describe what needs to be done: 880 1# \$6 100-01/(B \$a Raṅasubhe, Sūryānārayaṇa, \$c Dr. Output Format: Provide the MARC record in a clear, tagged format. Note: Provide only MARC formatted bibliographic data, nothing else.

Provide JSON Schema: Enabled when Response Format is set to JSON Schema

Preview History Starred

value: কথা-কবিতার কথকতা / গোস্বামী, সত্রাজিৎ কথা-কবিতার কথকতা / সত্রাজিৎ গোস্বামী - কলকাতা ; পরম্পরা প্রকাশন, 2019 - 167 p. 21 cm. ISBN: 9789380869681 250 Subjects--Topical Terms: Bengali essays Dewey Class. No.: B 891.444 / Go 534 kat

response: সত্রাজিৎ গোস্বামী
264 #1 \$6 880-03 \$a কলকাতা : \$b পরম্পরা প্রকাশন, \$c 2019.
300 ## \$a 167 p. ; \$b 21 cm.
020 #a 9789380869681 : \$6 880-04
650 ## \$a বাংলা প্রবন্ধ : \$6 880-05
082 #0 \$a B 891.444 / Go 534 kat : \$6 880-06
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Figure-7: Automated Multilingual MARC 21 Record Generation

8. CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

The study systematically demonstrates that sovereign LLMs such as Sarvam-105B are a strategic requirement for the digital sovereignty of Indian libraries rather than just experimental tools. This study illustrates that a domestic Indic-centric model can perform complex library tasks from translation to cataloging with the same professional efficiency as global proprietary LLMs like Gemini 2.5 Pro by utilizing the five core case studies that were initially proposed in our prior research. The outcome of the research shows that Sarvam-105B has excellent linguistic precision in Bengali script processing through minimizing the translation loss that is commonly associated with western-centric LLMs due to the lack of training in regional corpora. Additionally, the flawless integration of this sovereign AI stack into the existing framework indicates that our national AI infrastructure is completely prepared to perform library technical operations. Finally, our research provides a roadmap for self-reliance in language accuracy and cultural nuances.

The successful implementation of Sarvam-105B opens up an array of revolutionary opportunities for the Indian library environment. Future research should explore how voice-to-voice LLMs like

Gnani-Dhwani can be integrated to generate multilingual 'agentic AI' reference desks that can help patrons in a wide range of regional dialects. Using vision language LLMs such as Patram7B to automate the digitization and metadata extraction of handwritten historical texts has a lot of possibilities. Other than that, the framework may be expanded to 'Edge AI' applications that allow small libraries to execute complex linguistic tasks remotely at the same time while protecting the personal information. In future research, to ensure flawless automatic cataloguing, sovereign models' training datasets should include national bibliographic data such as the Indian National Bibliography (INB). Lastly, to achieve real national linguistic coverage in digital information retrieval, we have to expand this framework via Bhasini that supports all 22 official languages of India.

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Annexure-I: Global Sovereign AI initiatives

Sl. No.	Name of the LLM and Latest Version	Name of the Country	Launched in	Developed by	Initiative Type	Parameters	Additional Details about the LLM
1	PanGu (PanGu 5.5)	China	2021	Huawei	Private	718 billion (MoE)	It focuses on industrial utility rather than general-purpose conversation. It has three layers L0 (Foundation), L1 (Industry-specific) and L2 (scenario-specific). It was the first model that used for weather forecasting.
2	BLOOM	France	2022	BigScience research workshop and HuggingFace	Collaborative	366 billion	BLOOM is a transformer-based LLM which is designed to generate text in 46 languages and 13 programming languages. The project led by HuggingFace and more than 700 volunteer researcher and engineer involved in this project. The model trained on approximately 366 billion parameters.
3	Mistral (Mistral Large 3)	France	2023	Mistral AI SAS	Startup	675 billion (Active 41 billion)	Mistral AI is the commercial version of French AI sovereignty launch in 2023. The first model of Mistral have 7 billion parameters and now the latest one named Mistral Large 3 have 675 billion parameters and it is a MoE model.
4	ERNIE Bot (ERNIE 5.0)	China	2023	Baidu	Private	2.4 trillion (MoE)	ERNIE (Enhanced Representation through Knowledge Integration) not just trained on text but also trained on knowledge graph and also used Kunlunxin M100/M300 chips and PaddlePaddle framework layer which is China's first independently developed open-source deep-learning platform
5	HyperCLOVA X	South Korea	2023	Naver	Private		HyperCLOVA X developed by Naver, in 2023 is an example of sovereign LLM which is trained on Korean language.

6	Jais (Jais 2)	UAE	2023	G42's Inception, Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence and Cerebras	Govt Initiative	70 billion	It produce high quality Arabic text.
7	ChatGLM (GLM 4.7)	China	2023	Zhipu AI	Startup	355 billion (MoE)	It is a bilingual (Chinese and English) research model
8	Qwen (Qwen3)	China	2023	Alibaba	Private	235 billion-MoE(Active 22 billions)	Qwen3 trained on total 119 languages and dialects for this AI Singapore utilized Qwen to build the latest model of SEA-LION. And it also worked as 'Agentic AI'
9	Hunyuan (Hunyuan-T1 and Hunyuan-TurboS)	China	2023	Tencent	Private	560 billions MoE	It is a multimodel AI family which is design for deep reasoning with high speed performance.
10	DeepSeek	China	2023	Hangzhou DeepSeek Artificial Intelligence Basic Technology Research Co., Ltd.	Startup	671 billion-MoE (Active 37 billion)	It was developed to reduced dependency on foreign English-centric proprietary models. It also aligns with China's "AI Plus" initiative and the 15th five-year plan (2026-2030) to integrate AI into national strategic infrastructure.
11	UlizaLlama (UlizaLlama 3)	Kenya	2023	Jacaranda Health		8 billion	Based on Llama 2 and Llama 3. It was fine-tuned on thousands of high-quality Swahili/English Q&A pairs related to maternal health, agriculture, and general education and understand local Eastern African context, social etiquette and linguistic variation in Kenya and Tanzania.
12	Fugaku-LLM	Japan	2024	Tokyo Institute of Technology, Tohoku University, Fujitsu Limited, RIKEN, Nagoya University, CyberAgent, and Kotoba Technologies	Govt Initiative	13 billion	Trained on domestic CPU-based infrastructure. Based on the architecture of GPT-2. Training data's 60% Japanese and 40% English, mathematics and codes.
13	TAIDE	Taiwan	2024	National Science and Technology Council (NSTC)	Govt Initiative	12-13 billion	The Trustworthy AI Dialogue Engine (TAIDE) is trained on Chinese dataset that is specific to Taiwan. It also developed

							by using the architecture of Llama 2 and Llama 3.
14	SEA-LION (SEA-LION V4)	Singapore	2024	AI Singapore (AISG)	Govt Initiative	Gemma-27 billions Qwen-32 billions	Southeast Asian Language in One Network (SEA-LION) is a indigenous open-source LLM that specifically based on Llama 3.1 and trained on 13 regional languages which advocates cultural and linguistic sovereignty.
15	Falcon (Falcon-H1R 7B)	UAE	2024	Technology Innovation Institute (TII)	Govt Initiative	7 billion	The model mainly trained on RefinedWeb which is a dataset of TII, and other scientific papers from PubMed and arXiv.
16	N-ATLAS	Nigeria	2025	Awarri, National Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR) and NITDA.	Collaborative	8 billion	The Nigerian Atlas for Languages & AI at Scale(N-ATLAS) built on Llama 3 architecture. It includes automatic speech recognition. The latest version focuses on regional languages of Nigeria like Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, and Nigerian-accented English
17	PLLuM (Llama-PLLuM-70B, PLLuM-8x7B)	Poland	2025	Wroclaw University of Technology (project leader), NASK – National Research Institute, the Information Processing Center – National Research Institute (OPI PIB), the Institute of Computer Science Foundations of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the University of Lodz and the Institute of Slavic Studies of the Polish Academy of Sciences	Govt Initiative	8 to 70 billion (Based on Mistral and Llama 3.1)	The Polish Large Language Model (PLLuM) developed in 2025 and have 8 to 70B parameters. This model also utilized in mObyzatel app which is a platform for Poland’s digital Id and citizen services. In this app PLLuM act as a virtual assistant to help the citizens of Poland.
18	OpenEuroLM	European Union	2025	Consortium of more than 20 institutes.	Community-led	7 to 70 billion	It covers total 35 languages and fully compliant with ‘EU AI Act’.
19	Viking / SiloLLM	Norway, Sweden and Finland	2025	Silo AI, University of Turku, and HPLT	Private	33 billion	Trained on low resource Nordic languages like Icelandic and also trained

							on European data to ensure it understand the local legal, cultural, and social nuances.
20	Apertus	Switzerland	2025	ETH Zurich, EPFL, & Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS)	Private	8 to 70 billion	Based on the architecture of Llama 3 but better in Swiss dialects, Romansh and many low resource languages. The training dataset, data-cleaning logs and evaluation code are available in public domain. It is a EU AI Act compliant LLM.
21	Sabiá (Sabiá-3)	Brazil	2025	Maritaca AI	Private	-	Based on Llama 3 and Mistral. Efficient in Portuguese language. Training dataset includes Brazilian legal documents. Government records, university exam, and filtered web data. In a evaluation on Brazilian Bar Exam Sabiá-3.1 scored better than GPT-4.
22	Latam-GPT	Latin America	2025	National Center for Artificial Intelligence (CENIA) and 30 other institutes across 12 countries in Latin America	Private	50 billion	The model trained on 2.6 million documents from 20 different countries and the dataset includes legal codes, local literature, and government documents.

Annexure-II: List of Prompts used in the case studies

Sl. No.	Name of the case Study	Prompt
1	Genderization	<p>You are a Bengali transliteration and name analysis expert. You will be given a list of author names where forenames and surnames are separated by ' '. Your tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transliterate each forename and surname into Bengali script - After the Bengali transliteration, append the gender in Bengali (পুরুষ for male, মহিলা for female, অজানা for ambiguous/unknown) - Infer gender from the forename only, based on common Bengali naming conventions - Separate the transliterated name and gender with ' - ' - Output one name per line, in the same order as the input - Do not translate the meaning — only transliterate the sounds into Bengali script - Do not add any explanation, numbering, or extra punctuation in the name list - After all names, add a blank line followed by a summary count in Bengali <p>Input format example: Sayan Pal Abir Das Soumita Roy</p> <p>Output format example: সায়ন পাল - পুরুষ</p>

		<p>অবির দাস - পুরুষ সৌমিতা রায় - মহিলা</p> <p>মোট পুরুষ লেখক: ২ মোট মহিলা লেখক: ১ মোট অজানা: ০</p> <p>Now transliterate, determine gender, and provide summary counts for the following:</p>
2	Translation	<p>Read the provided corpus carefully and translate it into Bengali. The translation must prioritize contextual equivalence over literal word-for-word substitution, ensuring that academic library terminology is rendered accurately for a native speaker. Maintain the formal tone suitable for scholarly metadata.</p>
3	Summarization	<p>Act as a professional Information Scientist and Academic Editor. Read the following technical abstract in Bengali, which discusses Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and Vector Databases. Summarize the core research objective and methodology into a lucid, scholarly 'TL;DR' in formal Bengali. The summary must be between 30 and 50 words and maintain the technical nuance of the original scholarly content. Output only the Bengali summary.</p>
4.1	Sentiment Analysis	<p>Perform a granular sentiment analysis on the following book reviews. For each review, identify the sentiment (positive-ইতিবাচক, negative-নেতিবাচক, or neutral-নিরপেক্ষ) and extract the specific reasoning. Ensure the analysis accounts for code-mixing (e.g., Hindi-English or Tamil-English) and cultural nuances in expression.</p> <p>Output the result in a structured format: [সিদ্ধান্ত-ইতিবাচক অথবা নেতিবাচক অথবা নিরপেক্ষ] -- [কারণ].</p>
4.2	Sentiment Analysis (through Indian language based prompt)	<p>নিম্নলিখিত বইয়ের পর্যালোচনাগুলির অনুভূতি বিশ্লেষণ করুন। প্রতিটি পর্যালোচনার জন্য, অনুভূতি সনাক্ত করুন (ইতিবাচক, নেতিবাচক, বা নিরপেক্ষ) এবং নির্দিষ্ট যুক্তি বের করুন। কোড-মিক্সিং (যেমন, হিন্দি-ইংরেজি বা তামিল-ইংরেজি) এবং অভিব্যক্তিতে সাংস্কৃতিক সূক্ষ্মতার জন্য বিশ্লেষণ অ্যাকাউন্টগুলি নিশ্চিত করুন।</p> <p>একটি কাঠামোগত বিন্যাসে ফলাফল প্রদান করুন: [সিদ্ধান্ত-ইতিবাচক বা নেতিবাচক অথবা নিরপেক্ষ] -- [কারণ]।</p>
5	Multilingual Bibliographic Record Generation	<p>Task: Act as a Library Metadata Specialist. Generate a MARC 21 record with Multi-script Linkage (Tag 880) based on the provided book data.</p> <p>Standard Operating Procedure (SOP):</p> <p>Script Placement: * Fields 100, 245, 260/264, 650: Use the Native Script (e.g., Devanagari).</p> <p>Tag 880: Use the Roman Transliteration (ALA-LC Romanization rules). Linkage Logic (\$6): In the Native Tag, add \$6 880-[NN] (where NN is the occurrence number). In the 880 Tag, add \$6 [Native Tag]-[NN]/(B (where (B signifies the Latin script).</p> <p>Indicators: Ensure indicators match MARC 21 standards (e.g., 100 1# for personal names, 245 10 for titles with a main entry).</p> <p>Example Entry (Use this structure): 100 1# \$6 880-01 \$a রণসুভে, সূর্যনারায়ণ, \$c ডা. 880 1# \$6 100-01/(B \$a Raṇasubhe, Sūryānārayaṇa, \$c Dr.</p> <p>Output Format: Provide the MARC record in a clear, tagged format.</p> <p>Note: Provide only MARC formatted bibliographic data, nothing else.</p>